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A Holistic Market Research Analysis of Carbon-Negative Fuel Systems embedding Decision-Making Procedures

Main-Authors: Gabriel Steffen¹, Fatima Dargam¹

¹REACH Innovation

Dietrichsteinplatz 6/9, 8010 Graz, Austria

f.dargam@reach-innovation.eu / g.steffen@reach-innovation.eu

www.reach-innovation.eu

**Co-Authors: Diego Marazza², Martin Meiller³, Daniele Molognoni⁴, Andrzej Szlęk⁵,
Nikolas Hagemann⁶, Simone Beutle¹**

²University of Bologna, ³Fraunhofer UMSICHT, ⁴LEITAT Technological Center, ⁵Silesian University of Technology, ⁶ITHAKA Institute

ABSTRACT

The transition toward sustainable and resilient energy systems requires robust decision-support methodologies that can evaluate complex technologies under dynamic regulatory, economic and environmental conditions. This paper presents a holistic workflow, which involved decision making procedures, implemented for the EU Horizon Europe project NET-Fuels. The project aims to develop and validate integrated novel thermochemical and bio-electrochemical technologies to produce sustainable carbon-negative advanced fuels from low grade waste biomass feedstock. To support opportunity identification and strategic deployment decisions, a Market and Competitive Research Analysis (MCRA) was conducted, applying well established analytical methodologies like SWOT, PESTEL and Porter's Five Forces (P5F). The MCRA workflow considered a compilation of technologies for advanced fuels generation (Tech-Watch), which embedded eligibility and heuristic filtering procedures, resulting in a curated set of competitive systems related to NET-Fuels. This triggered further analysis using the three analytical methodologies, which derived a well positioning of the NET-Fuels integrated solution within the current research and development landscape, providing strategic insights for the definition of appropriate business cases to be validated by the project. This paper presents the way that the MCRA has contributed to valuable decision-making for further implementation of the involved emerging technologies of carbon-negative advanced fuels, supporting a sustainable pathway for energy transition.

Keywords: Market and Competitive Research Analysis (MCRA), SWOT, PESTEL, Porter's Five Forces, Carbon-Negative Advanced Fuels, NET-Fuels Project, Business-Cases, Bio-Energy-Carbon-Capture-Utilisation-Storage (BECCUS), Energy Transition.

1. Introduction

Achieving sustainable and resilient transitions in the energy sector requires decision-support methodologies capable of handling technological complexity, multi-level uncertainties, and interdependent socio-economic factors. Decision Support Systems (DSS) play a crucial role in aiding policymakers, industries, and technology developers in evaluating new pathways for renewable fuels and carbon-negative systems. The NET-Fuels project develops an innovative, modular BECCUS-based system integrating Thermo-Catalytic Reforming (TCR), hydrogen separation (PSA), oxyfuel

combustion, and Bio-Electrochemical Methanation (BEM). Through this integrated process, NET-Fuels produces hydrogen, biomethane, TCR-oil for further upgrading, high-quality biochar for certified carbon removal, and purified CO₂ streams for internal use or storage. The Market and Competitive Research Analysis provides extensive background on the technological landscape, regulatory frameworks, competing systems, and socio-economic drivers. This paper demonstrates how three classical market intelligence analysis methods, SWOT, PESTEL and Porter’s Five Forces, can be combined into a holistic decision-support workflow to assist strategic deployment planning for negative-emission biofuel systems. In doing so, it further illustrates how this approach can be translated into concrete use cases by tracing the reasoning steps and decision pathways that link analytical findings to actionable deployment scenarios.

1.1. The NET-Fuels Project

NET-Fuels envisages to demonstrate a platform for the pilot-scale treatment of at least three residue streams, digestate obtained from manure and maize silage, pruning residues from special crops (apple or grapes) and low value forestry wood. The core NET-Fuels system comprises the following technologies: (i) the Thermo-Catalytic Reforming (TCR®), for biomass pyrolysis, generating solid biochar, liquid crude oil (TCR-oil) and tail gas; (ii) the Oxyfuel Combustion for enhanced energy recovery and CO₂ management; and (iii) the Bio-Electrochemical Methanation (BEM) to upgrade captured CO₂ into synthetic methane [1]. These technologies are illustrated in Figure 1.

The NET-Fuels process can be summarized as follows: Waste biomass feedstock is converted into bio-oil, biochar and syngas via TCR®; Hydrogen is separated from the syngas by Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) and the residual tail gas is combusted in an oxygen atmosphere (oxyfuel combustion) to obtain pure and

process heat; Further CO₂ is extracted from the exhaust gas and converted into methane via Bio-Electrochemical Methanation; and The biochar is applied as soil amendment in the agricultural sector producing a carbon sink [1].

2. MCRA Methodology

The methodological approach used in this study is based on a structured and multi-layered workflow that combines technological scoping, competitive market and research analysis and macro-environmental assessment. A part of this work was presented in [2] and fully developed in [3]. The process began with an extensive *Technology-Watch* phase, in which more than two hundred initiatives, technologies and projects relevant to biofuels, BECCUS technologies and renewable energy pathways were identified. This research drew on specialized databases, scientific publications and project repositories to map innovations situated within the wider carbon-negative fuel and energy ecosystem. The collected entries were subjected to an eligibility filtering procedure, which criteria included alignment with second-generation biomass, carbon-negative or carbon-neutral objectives, sustainability considerations and the explicit exclusion of first-generation biofuels due to ILUC-related (Indirect Land Use Change) and Fuels vs. Food constraints. This filtering step significantly reduced uncertainty and enabled a manageable and analytically consistent set of benchmark technologies. The filtered results formed the basis for a comprehensive SWOT analysis [4, 5, 6]. A baseline SWOT for the NET-Fuels system was developed to capture intrinsic strengths such as carbon negativity, feedstock flexibility, modularity and multi-output valorisation. In parallel, individual SWOT profiles were created for more than thirty relevant technologies contained in the competitive technologies database, capturing their technical, market-related and regulatory characteristics. This dual-perspective analysis enabled the

identification of structural patterns across the competitive landscape, and of comparative insights into technology positioning. To extend the analytical depth, the SWOT layer was complemented by a PESTEL [7] assessment, which macro-environmental analysis integrated political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors that influence the deployment of advanced biofuel and BECCUS solutions. The analysis identified several key drivers, most notably the regulatory shifts under RED III [8, 9], the anticipated tightening of the EU ETS [10], economic pressures from volatile fossil fuel markets, and the rising strategic value of certified carbon sequestration via biochar.

The PESTEL analysis placed the technology-centred SWOT results into a broader systemic context. In the sequel, the competitive dynamics of the market was analysed using the P5F [11] methodology. This step provided a structured assessment of the threat of substitutes, the bargaining power of suppliers and buyers, the intensity of rivalries and the relevance of entry barriers in the renewable fuels and CCUS-related markets. Insights from this analysis mainly revealed the strong competitive pressure exerted by alternative low-carbon fuel pathways, such as green hydrogen, biomethane and e-fuels; as well as the negotiating power of industrial buyers such as refineries and chemical clusters.

The integration of the three analytical tools (SWOT, PESTEL, P5F) in NET-Fuels' Market Competitive Research Analysis, provided a holistic view of both internal capabilities and external conditions. Their synthesis allowed the identification of robust strategic deployment configuration-options, with the definition of four options for business-cases. This MCRA multi-method approach forms the core contribution of the decision-support workflow presented in this paper.

3. Strategic Decision-Making: Combining SWOT, PESTEL, and P5F

The integration of the three analytical layers produced a multidimensional framework that showed the strategic positioning of the NET-Fuels technology, and guided the identification of viable deployment scenarios. By examining the outcomes of the SWOT analyses across both the NET-Fuels baseline and the competing technologies documented in the database, recurring thematic clusters emerged. Strength-related aspects such as the potential for carbon negativity, high feedstock flexibility, the modular architecture of the system and the ability to generate several economically relevant outputs proved to be consistently advantageous when compared to existing technologies. At the same time, the weaknesses identified, especially the technology readiness gap of the BEM unit and the high capital expenditure associated with thermochemical conversion systems, were found to be critical factors to be mitigated through appropriate deployment strategies, including modular and stepwise integration.

When placed together with the PESTEL results, the SWOT findings gained additional explanatory power. Political drivers, such as the implementation of RED III and broader Fit-for-55 [12] measures, reinforce the relevance of carbon-negative systems, particularly where certified carbon removal can enhance market positioning. Economic factors, including the cost volatility of fossil resources and the emerging markets for carbon credits, directly amplify the value proposition of multi-output systems such as NET-Fuels. Environmental considerations such as the role of biochar as a long-term carbon sink, which is essential for achieving durable negative emissions, further strengthen the strategic fit of the technology. Legal requirements, especially the upcoming obligations for biogas plants to demonstrate greenhouse gas performance, highlight the importance of flexible systems that can complement or replace existing upgrading technologies.

P5F analysis added a further analytical dimension by situating NET-Fuels within the competitive dynamics of the broader renewable fuels market. The high threat of substitutes, driven by rapidly evolving alternatives such as hydrogen, biomethane and electrification pathways, underlines the importance of technological differentiation. NET-Fuels' ability to provide multiple outputs, including renewable methane, hydrogen and bio-oil, combined with its capacity for carbon removal, emerged as a strategically relevant source of differentiation. The moderate to high bargaining power of industrial energy buyers confirmed the need for reliable, scalable and infrastructure-compatible solutions. The analysis also clarified that while entry barriers in the sector are substantial due to regulatory complexity, supply chain requirements and technological maturity thresholds, the modularity of the NET-Fuels system reduces these barriers by allowing smaller-scale deployment and retrofit pathways.

Combining the results across all three analytical dimensions, using SWOT, PESTEL and Porter’s Five Forces, the MCRA could support well-informed, structured and transparent decision-making in the context of emerging negative-emission technologies. The holistic integration of the three methods allowed the transformation of heterogeneous analytical insights into actionable strategic recommendations, demonstrating the practical validity of the decision-support workflow.

Figure 2: SWOT-PESTEL-P5F integrated in MCRA.

Table 1: Cross-method Insight-Matrix used for the MCRA

SWOT factor	PESTEL Driver	P5F Influence	Decision Insight
Feedstock flexibility	Abundant low-value biomass	Low supplier power	Locational advantage for rural deployment
Carbon negativity	RED III incentives	High buyer demand	Supports premium markets & carbon credit revenue
TRL gaps in BEM	High tech funding availability	Rivalry moderate	Justifies targeted pilot deployment
High CAPEX	Volatile energy markets	Substitute threat	Favors modular deployment + stepwise integration

Table 1 presents an integrated insight matrix that cross-maps key SWOT factors with corresponding PESTEL drivers and competitive pressures identified through P5F. By structuring these interdependencies, the matrix shows how internal technological characteristics are reinforced, constrained, or reshaped by external regulatory, economic, and market conditions. In doing so, the matrix displays the decision-making workflow within the MCRA, supporting transparent prioritisation of strategically robust deployment pathways for the NET-Fuels system.

4. Definition of Business Cases

The MCRA strategic analysis, also enabled the identification of four deployment pathways that demonstrate strong strategic, technological and economic feasibility. These include: the full NET-Fuels system for large industrial sites such as refineries and biogas plants; standalone BEM integration for biogas upgrading in response to upcoming regulatory requirements; TCR-based bio-oil production for maritime fuel blending; and the TCR + oxyfuel configuration for agro-industrial clusters where industrial symbiosis and circular resource utilisation can be leveraged. Each of these pathways reflects a convergence between internal strengths, external enablers and manageable competitive pressures, providing a well-founded basis for deployment planning. Table 2 presents the four configurations for Business Cases (BC) options for practical deployment-installations of the NET-Fuels technologies.

Table 2: NET-Fuels Business Cases Options

Business Cases	Exploitation Pathway	Scenarios
(1) Industrial-scale Biofuel Production	TCR + Oxyfuel + BEM	Refinery / Biogas Plant
(2) Decentralized BEM for Biogas Upgrading	BEM	Biogas Plant
(3) Maritime Fuel Blending Pilot	TCR	Refinery
(4) Deployment in Rural Agro-Industrial Settings	TCR + Oxyfuel	Refinery / Biogas Plant

4.1. Business-Case 1: Industrial-scale Biofuel Production

The full NET-Fuels configuration—integrating TCR, PSA-based hydrogen separation, oxyfuel combustion and bio-electrochemical methanation, emerged as a priority pathway particularly well-suited for industrial settings such as refineries and large biogas plants. This option leverages the system’s strongest internal characteristics identified in the SWOT analysis, including feedstock flexibility, multi-output valorisation and carbon negativity. At the same time, it directly responds to key PESTEL drivers, most notably the tightening of the RED III, the growing emphasis on certified carbon removals, and the increasing relevance

Figure 3: Business Case 1 Configuration.

of hydrogen and synthetic methane in industrial decarbonisation strategies. In competitive terms, the full configuration differentiates itself through its ability to internally utilise CO₂ streams and avoid reliance on external upgrading infrastructure, addressing several of the competitive pressures identified through P5F.

4.2. Business-Case 2: Biogas Upgrading

The second deployment pathway focuses on the standalone application of the BEM unit as a biogas upgrading solution. This pathway was strongly shaped by legal and political factors identified in the MCRA PESTEL layer, particularly the requirement for biogas operators to demonstrate greenhouse gas performance and comply with sustainability certification frameworks from 2026 onwards. Through the SWOT analysis, the BEM technology was identified as a component still developing toward higher TRL levels but offering significant strategic potential due to its ability to convert raw CO₂ within biogas into additional synthetic methane. When considered against the competitive analysis, the BEM deployment represents a clear value proposition, as it directly replaces or complements existing upgrading technologies, which are capital-intensive, operationally demanding and often result in the emission of concentrated CO₂ streams.

4.3. Business-Case 3: Maritime Fuel Blending Pilot

Figure 4: Business Case 3 Configuration.

A third deployment pathway was identified around the use of the TCR system as a standalone unit for producing high-quality bio-oil suitable for maritime fuel blending. This pathway aligns particularly well with technological strengths such as the high stability and low oxygen content of TCR-oil, which differentiates it from conventional fast-pyrolysis oils. From a MCRA PESTEL perspective, this option is shaped by regulatory developments in maritime decarbonisation and the need for low-sulphur, low-carbon fuels. Within the competitive landscape, this pathway positions NET-Fuels as a complementary solution that addresses the

maritime sector's reliance on heavy fuel oil and the urgent need to diversify its decarbonisation strategies beyond electrification and e-fuels.

4.4. Business-Case 4: Simplified Agro-Industrial Setup

The fourth deployment pathway concerns the integration of TCR and oxyfuel combustion in agro-industrial settings, particularly where industrial symbiosis and circular resource utilisation can be achieved [13]. This scenario draws on environmental and economic opportunities highlighted in the MCRA PESTEL analysis, such as the valorisation of agricultural residues, reduced transportation distances for feedstock and local utilisation of heat and CO₂ streams. Combined with insights from P5F, this pathway also benefits from comparatively low supplier power in agricultural regions and an increasing demand for circular production models in rural industrial clusters. The SWOT analysis further confirmed that the modularity of the system and the high-quality biochar output contribute significantly to the feasibility of such decentralised integrations.

Figure 5: Business Case 4 Configuration.

The four Business Cases' exploitation pathways represent deployment scenarios, in which internal capabilities, external incentives and competitive conditions converge in a robust manner. They reflect not only technological feasibility but also strategic fit within evolving regulatory frameworks and market environments. The identification of these pathways demonstrates how a multi-layered analytical

workflow can translate complex datasets into clear and actionable decision-support outputs.

5. Discussions and Conclusion

The market analysis workflow presented in this paper is characterised by a stepwise reduction of complexity, in which each analytical layer of the used tools (SWOT, PESTEL and P5F) progressively sharpened the strategic MCRA focus. Beginning with a broad spectrum of technological possibilities and market conditions, the workflow narrowed this field by repeatedly confronting preliminary insights with additional contextual information. In this iterative structure, each stage served as both an extension and a filter: insights that remained robust across multiple analytical perspectives moved forward, while options that conflicted with identified constraints or lacked strategic coherence were excluded. This cumulative reasoning created a transparent chain of justification, which resulted in the transition from initial exploration to concrete deployment scenarios, in a traceable and reproducible way. Hence, the overall MCRA method ensured that the final decisions were grounded, emerging from a balanced assessment of feasibility, relevance and contextual fit rather than from isolated criteria. Moreover, the workflow did not produce a singular optimal solution. Instead, it led a stable subset of deployment options that remained viable after successive rounds of analytical scrutiny.

In conclusion, the integrated decision-making approach taken by the MCRA implemented for NET-Fuels, strengthens the reliability of strategic planning by linking analytical evidence to actionable recommendations. It demonstrates how multi-layered MCRA workflow can be operationalised as a coherent decision-support method, enabling informed, defensible and adaptable choices in complex innovation and transition contexts. The approach is particularly suited to emerging energy technologies, where uncertainties are high and long-term conditions may shift. By structuring the reasoning process, the framework supports strategic clarity while preserving flexibility.

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6. References

- [1] Meiller M. et al.; NET-Fuels –Integrating negative emission technologies in biofuels production. DGMK/ÖGEW/SCI-Conference 2025, Essen, Germany. 28-29 October, 2025. Paper DOI:10.5281/zenodo18377185 [\[Link\]](#); Presentation DOI:10.5281/zenodo18377388. [\[Link\]](#)
- [2] Dargam F., Steffen G., Beutle S., Marazza D., Meiller M., Groves C., Molognomi D., Hagemann N., Szlek A., Langley M.; On a Potential Industrial Scale-up Roadmap for the NET-Fuels Project. Proc. of the 8th Central European Biomass Conference CEBC-2026, ISBN:978-3-9504380-9-3 DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18429981. [\[Link\]](#)
- [3] European Commission, Horizon Europe Project [NET-Fuels](#) (2022), GA# 101083780, Deliverable D5.1: NET-Fuels Market and Competitive Research Analysis. Ref.: Ares(2024)7725650, 30/10/2024.
- [4] Puyt R.W., Birger Lie F., Wilderom C.P.M. (2023). The Origin of SWOT Analysis. Long Range Planning, Elsevier, Volume 56, Issue 3, June 2023, DOI: 10.1016/j.lrp.2023.102304. [\[Link\]](#)
- [5] Pahl, N., & Richter, A. (2007). SWOT Analysis - Idea, Methodology and a Practical Approach. GRIN Verlag.
- [6] Emet GÜREL (2017). SWOT Analysis: A theoretical Review, The Journal of International Social Research, Volume: 10 Issue: 51 Aug. 2017. DOI: 10.17719/jisr.2017.1832. [\[Link\]](#)
- [7] Spencer T. (2016), PEST Analysis. Template available in [www.spencertom.com](#), 2016. [\[Link\]](#)
- [8] Directive (EU) 2023/2413 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023, amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 and Directive 98/70/EC, RED III - EU Renewable Energy Directive. PE/36/2023/REV/2. [\[Link\]](#). [9] RED III – 2023/2413/EU Directive – [\[Link\]](#).
- [10] EU ETS: Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and Council of 13 October 2003 establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Union and amending Council Directive 96/61/EC. [\[Link\]](#)
- [11] Porter M.E. (1979), How Competitive Forces Shape Strategy, Harvard Business Review, Reprint 79208. [\[Link\]](#)
- [12] Fit-for-55: The European climate law makes reaching the EU's climate goal of reducing EU emissions by at least 55% by 2030 a legal obligation. [\[Link\]](#).
- [13] Marazza D., Chiara D., Dargam F., Steffen G., Beutle S., Meiller M., Groves C., Petela K., Proniewicz M., Molognomi D., Vega-Paredes M., Hagemann N., Langley M.; Industrial and rural partnerships underpinned by biomass-based solutions for carbon removal, chemicals, and renewable energy — the NET-Fuels project. ECOMONDO - The Green Technology Expo 2025 (ECOMONDO 2025), Rimini, Italy, 04-07 November, 2025. Abstract DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18819204. [\[Link\]](#); Presentation DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18819486. [\[Link\]](#)